

DACAPO: Data fusion in operating room

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Abstract: Modern operating rooms (ORs) are equipped with numerous devices that generate large amounts of data, creating opportunities and challenges for medical teams. Current systems rely on the expertise of medical staff to process and interpret these data streams in real time. The OR of the future requires intelligent systems capable of interpreting and analysing multi-source data to provide context-aware support. This project aims to develop approaches for surgical workflow recognition, a crucial component in such systems, targeting three key tasks. Machine learning and deep learning approaches were employed to tackle surgical smoke detection, surgical tool classification, and surgical phase recognition. Achieved results demonstrate high performance of the developed models and the potential of integrating them into real practice.

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I. Introduction

Operating rooms (ORs) are becoming increasingly complex environments due to the incorporation of advanced medical devices, each designed to support medical teams inside the operating room. These devices generate large amount of data, which provide critical information about the patient's condition and surgical progress. However, this abundance of technology presents the challenge of managing and interpreting these data streams in real-time. Currently, surgical teams rely on their experience and knowledge to interpret the data coming from various devices. The future of operating operations will involve intelligent systems that can analyse this data in real time, provide relevant information to human operators and support medical teams in decision-making. Such systems can promote better communication and collaboration between medical teams. Furthermore, data-driven assistance systems have the potential to optimize workflow, avoid possible complications or hazards, and improve the patient outcome.

Analysing the surgical workflow is a crucial component to develop such intelligent systems. This project presents approaches for analysing the surgical workflow using laparoscopic videos. Laparoscopic videos offer important source of information about surgical actions, tackled organs or tissues and surgical tools. Analysing these data allows understanding surgical processes. This project handled three tasks which are surgical smoke detection, surgical tool classification and surgical phase recognition.

II. Material and methods

This project aims to recognise surgical workflow of laparoscopic procedures by focusing on three key tasks: smoke detection, tool classification and phase recognition.

II.I. Data

Videos were recorded at 25 Hz during laparoscopic procedures. The data collection was carried out at a clinic in

Villingen-Schwenningen, Germany [1]. The collected videos were anonymised by replacing image frames when the camera is outside the patient body with blank images. After anonymisation, videos were annotated with the class and location of surgical tools presented in the scene. To evaluate the performance of the proposed smoke detection approach, 258333 laparoscopic images were annotated for smoke presence.

Additionally, publicly-access datasets such as the Cholec80 dataset [2] were used for training and validating the developed models. This dataset includes 80 laparoscopic videos and labels for surgical tools and phases.

II.II. Smoke detection

Surgical smoke, emitted from electrosurgical devices, can obstruct the laparoscopic camera's view. Smoke detection is a crucial step toward the development of an automated smoke removal system, which will ensure a clear surgical field and improve procedural visibility for surgeons. Handcrafted features such as texture and color features were developed to distinguish smoke in the scene. Then an SVM model was trained using these features to detect smoke presence in laparoscopic images [3,4].

II.III. Surgical tool classification

Identifying surgical tools in laparoscopic images is a challenging task, as they can be occluded by smoke, blood or anatomical tissues. Thus, deep learning models, in particular convolutional neural networks (CNNs), were employed to perform surgical tool classification. CNNs are well-suited for image recognition tasks due to their ability to automatically learn complex features from training data. To further enhance the performance of CNN, attention modules were integrated, allowing the model to focus on the most relevant regions in the image. Additionally, a feature fusion approach was applied to improve robustness and generalisability of the model [5,6]. To model the temporal dependencies along laparoscopic videos, a long short-term memory (LSTM) model was combined with the

CNN model [7,8]. Moreover, a weakly-supervised tool localization approach was proposed to detect the location of surgical tools in the images using only tool presence binary labels [9,10].

II.IV. Surgical phase recognition

Surgical phases represent the main surgical steps within a procedure, each involving the use of specific surgical tools and the execution of certain surgical actions. While CNN models effectively extract spatial information from individual frames, phase recognition is time-dependent, requiring the integration of temporal models to capture the sequential dependencies over time. Therefore, CNNs were combined with temporal models to leverage spatio-temporal information encoded in the laparoscopic videos. Several temporal models were explored for surgical phase recognition, including NARX neural network [11], Hidden Markov model (HMM) [12,13] and LSTM network [14]. Since there is a strong correlation between surgical tools used and the surgical phase, a joint model was developed to recognize both tools and phases simultaneously [15]. The model used CNN, attention modules and LSTM. Additionally, a multi-map convolutional layer was integrated, allowing the model to perform tool localisation.

III. Results and discussion

This project introduces video-based approaches for analysing surgical workflow of the laparoscopic procedures. The proposed approaches achieved high performance for various recognition tasks. The SVM model achieved an accuracy of 91% for detecting smoke in laparoscopic images. Experimental results show that the model can detect the smoke regardless of its density in the scene, i.e. low density or fog. That indicates that the designed handcrafted features are effective for distinguishing the smoke.

CNN architectures have demonstrated strong performance in classifying surgical tools, with ResNet-50 achieving an average precision of 92% on the Cholec80 dataset. Incorporating temporal information further enhanced the classification performance, except for the grasper. Since graspers are frequently employed to hold or manipulate tissues during the entire procedure, temporal models cannot learn distinctive temporal features for this tool. However, the frequent presence of the grasper allows the CNN to learn discriminative spatial features for accurate identification.

Moreover, combining features at multiple stages of the CNN model has significantly improved its generalizability. Results showed a 7% improvement in the model's performance when applied to data from unseen surgical sites and different types of procedures. This demonstrates the benefit of multi-stage feature fusion in enhancing the robustness and adaptability of CNN models across varied surgical environments.

Recurrent neural networks demonstrate superior performance compared to NARX and Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) for surgical phase recognition, due to their ability to better capture temporal dependencies. Additionally, multi-task learning significantly enhances

performance in target tasks, as the model learns more effective and shared features across tasks. The developed CNN-LSTM-based approach jointly performs surgical tool classification, localization, and phase recognition. This model achieved a mean average precision of 96% for tool classification, a 70% F1-score for tool localization, and 89% precision for surgical phase recognition.

IV. Conclusions

This project presents video-based approaches for analysing surgical workflow in laparoscopic procedures. The proposed models for smoke detection, tool classification, and phase recognition achieved high performance, paving the way for the development of many potential applications to assist healthcare providers intra- and post-operatively.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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REFERENCES

- [1] Abdulbaki Alshirbaji T, Aldeen Jalal N, et al. Data Recording Framework for Physiological and Surgical Data in Operating Theatres. *Current Directions in Biomedical Engineering* 2020;6:364–7.
- [2] Twinanda AP, Shehata S, et al. Endonet: a deep architecture for recognition tasks on laparoscopic videos. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 2016;36:86–97.
- [3] Alshirbaji TA, Jalal NA, et al. Classifying smoke in laparoscopic videos using SVM. *Current Directions in Biomedical Engineering* 2017;3:191–4.
- [4] Jalal NA, Alshirbaji TA, et al. Features for detecting smoke in laparoscopic videos. *Current Directions in Biomedical Engineering* 2017;3:521–4.
- [5] Alshirbaji TA, Jalal NA, et al. Improving the Generalisability of Deep CNNs by Combining Multi-stage Features for Surgical Tool Classification, *IEEE*; 2022, p. 533–6.
- [6] Tamer AA, Jalal NA, et al. Robustness of Convolutional Neural Networks for Surgical Tool Classification in Laparoscopic Videos from Multiple Sources and of Multiple Types 2022.
- [7] Alshirbaji TA, Jalal NA, et al. A deep learning spatial-temporal framework for detecting surgical tools in laparoscopic videos. *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control* 2021;68:102801.
- [8] Jalal NA, Abdulbaki Alshirbaji T, et al. Surgical Tool Detection in Laparoscopic Videos by Modeling Temporal Dependencies Between Adjacent Frames, Springer; 2020, p. 1045–52.
- [9] Jalal NA, Alshirbaji TA, et al. Surgical tool classification & localisation using attention and multi-feature fusion deep learning approach. *IFAC-PapersOnLine* 2023;56:5626–31.
- [10] Zia A, Bhattacharyya K, et al. Surgical tool classification and localization: results and methods from the MICCAI 2022 SurgToolLoc challenge. *arXiv Preprint arXiv:230507152* 2023.
- [11] Jalal NA, Alshirbaji TA, et al. Predicting surgical phases using CNN-NARX neural network. *Current Directions in Biomedical Engineering* 2019;5:405–7.
- [12] Jalal NA, Abdalnaki Alshirbaji T, et al. Evaluating convolutional neural network and hidden markov model for recognising surgical phases in sigmoid resection. *Current Directions in Biomedical Engineering* 2018;4:415–8.
- [13] Jalal NA, Abdulbaki Alshirbaji T, et al. The effect of Hierarchical Hidden Markov Model on Phase Recognition in Laparoscopic Videos, Pabst; 2018, p. 61–3.
- [14] Jalal NA, Alshirbaji TA, et al. A deep learning framework for recognising surgical phases in laparoscopic videos. *IFAC-PapersOnLine* 2021;54:334–9.
- [15] Jalal NA, Alshirbaji TA, et al. Laparoscopic video analysis using temporal, attention, and multi-feature fusion based-approaches. *Sensors* 2023;23:1958.